

3. Further evidence is obtained to support the view suggested earlier that coagulation is not time-continuous but 'zonal,' and that this feature becomes more pronounced the *slower* the change.

4. It is suggested that both the viscosity and transparency (and therefore opacity) in colloids are functions partly of micellar constants such as the charge, size and specially the shape, etc., and of certain bulk or macroscopic properties of the system as a whole and that the latter might be the more potent factor.

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Studies in the Anthraquinone Series. Attempts to synthesise Anthraquinone Carboxylic Acids of the Morindone Type.

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Among the naturally occurring anthraquinone derivatives, carboxylic acids are known only in the madder and emodin groups. The acids occurring in madder are munjisthin and pseudo-purpurin while those belonging to the emodin group are rhein and emodic acid. It appeared to us to be of interest to synthesise acids of the morindone type, which might occur in natural products.

An anthraquinone derivative of the morindone type containing a carboxyl group and not less than two hydroxyl groups may have one or other of four alternative formulae A to D.

We have synthesised the β -methyl ether of (A) by oxidising 1-acetoxy-2-methoxy-6-methylantraquinone (Mitter and Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 776) with chromic acid and deacetylating the product. It forms red silky needles, melting at 195° .

Our next idea was to synthesise the acid (D). Now the usual laboratory oxidation processes are not suitable for the oxidation of methyl groups, with adjacent hydroxyl groups, into carboxyl groups (Mitter and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 635). In this connection, mention may also be made of the case of mujisthin, which could not be obtained by the direct oxidation of rubiadin. We, therefore, tried a procedure similar to that adopted by Jacobson and Adams for the synthesis of a derivative of morindone (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2788).

Opianic acid was condensed with methyl 5-bromosalicylate in presence of sulphuric acid, when 5:6-dimethoxy-2 (2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-bromophenyl) phthalide (I) was obtained as white crystals, m.p. 215° . This was reduced with zinc dust and caustic soda in boiling solution under mechanical stirring for 15 hours. The dibasic acid so obtained (II) melted at 225° . Several ring-closure experiments were tried with (II) with a view to obtain the corresponding anthrone. It was treated with sulphuric acid in the cold as well as with heating. In the former case it remained unchanged while in the latter complete sulphonation took place. We also tried phosphorus pentoxide but without success. It is well known that hydroxy compounds having *para*-positions to the hydroxyl groups free, are easily sulphonated. So the acid was brominated, when a monobromo derivative, presumably the *p*-bromo derivative (*cf.* Jacobson and Adams, *loc. cit.*) melting at 210° , was obtained. Ring-closure experiments with this compound also met with no better success.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5:6-Dimethoxy-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-carbomethoxy-5'-bromophenyl)-phthalide (I).—Methyl 5-bromosalicylate (5 g.), opianic acid (3.6 g.) and sulphuric acid (13 c.c., 1 part of water in 6 parts of concentrated acid) were mixed thoroughly in a mortar and allowed to stand for 2 days when the mass became green. On adding water, heavy granular precipitate separated which, after washing with water, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 215°, yield 3 g. (Found: Br, 17.9. $C_{18}H_{15}O_7Br$ requires Br, 18.9 per cent).

An acetyl derivative was obtained on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine, m.p. 210° after crystallisation from glacial acetic acid. (Found: Br, 17.26. $C_{20}H_{17}O_8Br$ requires Br, 17.20 per cent).

5:6-Dimethoxy-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-bromophenyl) phthalide.—The phthalide (1 part) was refluxed with 10% KOH (5 parts) for 3 hours. On dilution and precipitation with hydrochloric acid, the acid was precipitated. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 253°. (Found: Br, 20.4. $C_{17}H_{13}O_7Br$ requires Br, 19.56 per cent).

5:6-Dimethoxy-2(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxybenzyl)-benzoic Acid (II).—The phthalide (I) (5 g.), 10% NaOH solution (104 c.c.) and zinc (17 g.) were introduced into a three-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a mechanical stirrer and the contents heated on a sand-bath under stirring for 15 hours. The excess of zinc was filtered off and concentrated hydrochloric acid added to the filtrate when a flocculent precipitate was formed. This was filtered, washed and dissolved in 10% soda solution. The filtrate was acidified, the precipitate washed free from hydrochloric acid and crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 225°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 61.7; H, 5.06. $C_{17}H_{13}O_7$ requires C, 61.4; H, 4.85 per cent).

5:6-Dimethoxy-2(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-bromobenzyl) benzoic Acid (III).—The benzoylbenzoic acid (II) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) by heating and after cooling bromine (0.16 c.c.) was added. The mixture was left overnight and then diluted. The precipitate was filtered, washed and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 210°. (Found: Br, 19.6. $C_{17}H_{13}O_7Br$ requires Br, 19.4 per cent).

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